

Sustainable sources of irrigation water and nitrogen are critical for the adaptation of European crop production to climate change

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- › Climate change will affect the yield potential of crops in different ways in different regions of Europe
- › In much of Europe there will be increased yield potential for crops
- › However, in southern and eastern regions there will be a strong decline in yield potential
- › To maximise yield potential and mitigate against yield declines both irrigating and maintaining nitrogen input is important. There are also some positive benefits of cultivar selection and rotation, but these are less significant.
- › To mitigate against the impact of climate change the main policy recommendation is to identify and promote sustainable sources of both water and nitrogen for crop production for future cropping systems.

Introduction

Crop plants are particularly sensitive to future changes in climate, both directly from changes in rainfall and temperature, but also indirectly through impacts on soil health by modifying soil function and water balances. The projected increases in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations will also have direct impacts on C3 (a type of photosynthesis adapted to mild temperatures used by most European crops except maize and sorghum) crop growth by increasing the resource use efficiency potential for radiation capture, water and nutrient use. This is a consequence of greater saturation of the CO₂ fixation process in C3 plants with elevated CO₂, allowing more C to be fixed per unit of resource. If the potential positive impacts of elevated CO₂ levels are to be realized, then we will need to manage and adapt to the negative consequences of climate change, including more extreme abiotic and biotic stress, which will vary spatially in Europe and temporally between and within growing seasons.

Wheat and potato are important crops in the European agricultural context, are ranked in the top five crops by production in the world, and are one of the few crop species delivering many of the calories and nutrients for people globally (FAO, 1995). Therefore, understanding

the patterns and the impacts of climate on the production of these critical crops is an important task that can help to aid policy support and the design of adaptation and mitigation strategies to tackle those changes of climate. Crop models have been identified as an alternative approach to increase the efficiency of agronomic experimentation in order to improve decision-making on the efficient utilization of resources. These process-based models can simulate plant and soil processes and their response to different environmental factors.

“The impact of climate change will be variable across Europe with many regions seeing greater potential yield for wheat, but other areas seeing severe declines in yield potential.”

Recent research in the SolACE project, using such crop models has delivered projections on the impact of a number of agronomic interventions on the adaptation and mitigation to climate change in both wheat and potato production in Europe.

Approach

We used the DSSAT model (more information available in Appendix A) to generate projections of crop production with climate change and the impact of a range of interventions on the outcome. We selected interventions from both those being trialed in SolACE and through preferences for interventions expressed through stakeholder engagement. These included

- the introduction of grain legumes in crop rotations as a replacement for nitrogen (N) fertilisers in both wheat and potatoes,
- reduced tillage in wheat as a practice that reduces soil evaporation compared to conventional deep tillage and saves water and
- suboptimal irrigation in wheat and potatoes as an adaptation practice in the face of the projected increase in precipitation variability with climate change.

Our aim was to evaluate the potential to reduce inputs of N fertilizer and what projected yields will be under this range of scenarios with and without climate change.

“In order to mitigate against the worst impacts of climate change in the south and east of Europe and to try and take advantage of the potential yield gains in north and west Europe, we need to consider how we will find a sustainable source of both irrigation water and nitrogen, i.e. sources that replace in-organic fertilisers and their large environmental footprint.”

Results

The SolACE modelling has demonstrated that for much of Europe the potential impact of climate change will be to increase yield potential of wheat and potatoes compared to current conditions and this is thought to be due to favorable changes in precipitation and temperature that allow the crops to take advantage of the increased atmospheric CO₂ in future environments (Figure 1). So, in conditions of non-limiting stress, greater atmospheric CO₂ will allow these C3 crops to fix more carbon and therefore improve water use efficiency (WUE) and nitrogen use efficiency (NUE). However, this is not likely to be the case where there are significant prevailing stresses. Therefore, it is important to note that the DSSAT model used here does not take account of evolving biotic stress, which is also likely to change with climate change and be particularly impactful on potato production which is particularly prone to fungal and oomycete diseases, especially in seed potato production. The importance of prevailing stress is seen when the climate predictions for yield of wheat in Eastern and Southern Europe are considered. Here we see the opposite of the North and West and large declines in yield are predicted (Figure 1), due to extreme temperatures and reduced availability of water at the start of the cropping season. It is clear that one way to mitigate this predicted decline in yield is to irrigate, and when this is done the extreme declines in wheat yield are reduced to zero (a 25 to 30% decline overturn) in these extremely hot and dry climates. The positive impact of irrigation on yield is also seen in the potato projections. Interestingly, for wheat there is also a positive effect in the regions projected to have severe reductions in yield when applying reduced or conservation tillage systems. This is presumably a result of the greater availability of water with these practices.

Also clear from our projections is that the maintained provision of nitrogen will be critical for mitigating the negative impacts of climate change in the south and east and for achieving the greatest yield increases in the north and west of Europe. While a small reduction in N application (two thirds of standard 220kg ha⁻¹) was possible with limited negative impacts, the total removal of N was detrimental in both the wheat and potato modelling scenarios. Interestingly, the use of a legume precrop had little or variable impact on mitigating the removal of N fertilisers in both wheat and potato production systems. In addition, there were significant impacts of cultivar selection on both wheat and potato, suggesting that there is some scope for matching the correct cultivars with the correct agronomy, but these effects were swamped by the strong impacts of a lack of water and a lack of nitrogen.

Figure 1. Relative yield change in respect to the baseline for two Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs; for more information see Appendix B) and as an average across three general circulation models (GCMs). The left-hand and central four panel maps represent the conventional cropping system for 2020–2050 and 2080–2100; while the adaptation option of low N, pea-wheat rotations and suboptimal irrigation for 2080–2100 is represented for the two right-hand panels.

Conclusion

Projections suggest that there is a clear divide in the response of agricultural production in two key crops, wheat and potatoes, across Europe. In the north, centre and west of Europe, production is projected to significantly increase. While in the south and east of Europe production is likely to significantly decline. These projections are dependent on mitigation against abiotic and biotic stress.

In order to mitigate against the worst impacts of climate change in the south and east of Europe and to try and take advantage of the potential yield gains in north and west Europe, we need to consider how we will find a sustainable source of both irrigation water and nitrogen, i.e. sources that replace inorganic fertilisers and their large environmental footprint. It will also be important to consider the potential impact of evolving biotic stress, which is not considered by the SolACE modelling.

Overall, the SolACE data highlights the importance and need for considering both the spatial and temporal variability in adaptation to climate change in crop production. Furthermore, it highlights the need for adaptation to be addressed at a seasonal and a local scale, rather than at a regional, national or even continental scale. To conclude, the implications and recommendations for policy makers are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. Implications and recommendations for policy makers.

Change in practice by farmer or agricultural support industry	Policy interventions to facilitate changes
Use sustainable irrigation to maximise potential yield in crops and minimize stress related to drought associated with climate change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Identify sustainable sources and uses of irrigation water in Europe. These could include waste/grey water or water generated from solar desalinization for example. › Identify the appropriate application technologies, rates and timing of irrigation water for different crops › Promote the role of advisors to promote the sustainable use of irrigation water.
Use sustainable sources of nitrogen to maximise potential yield in crops and minimize stress associated with climate change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Identify sustainable sources and uses of nitrogen in Europe. This could include rotation or intercropping with legumes, microbial inoculants or use of organic amendments from waste streams. › Identify the appropriate application technologies, rates and timing of nitrogen for different crops › Promote role of advisors to promote the sustainable use of alternative nitrogen sources.
Use conservation tillage practices in arable crops to maximise soil function and minimize water loss	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Promote role of advisors to promote the use of conservation tillage approaches to improve water use. Incentivisation through the EU Green deal and farm payment schemes could be used.
Select the appropriate crop varieties that have the ability to cope with climate change related stress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Identify optimal varieties of crop species for resilience to climate change related stress at a local scale. This could be facilitated by increased funding for research and development in breeding. › Promote role of advisors to help select the appropriate varieties for a given locale and cropping system.
Select the appropriate crop rotations to maximise resilience to stress associated with climate change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Identify optimal crop rotations for resilience to climate change related stress at a local scale. › Promote role of advisors to help select the appropriate crop rotations for a given locale and cropping system.
Identify sustainable sources of water and nitrogen at a regional/local scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Identify sustainable sources of and approaches to using water and nitrogen in agriculture and provide legislation and advice to promote the use of the appropriate resources and technologies
Provide advice on the appropriate combination of interventions to mitigate against climate change related stress at a local scale.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Promote engagement of local advisors with modelers to promote combinations of interventions specific to that region.

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Appendices

Appendix A:

The Decision Support System for Agrotechnology Transfer (DSSAT) version 4.7.5 model was used to run the wheat and potato simulations (Hoogenboom et al., 2019; Jones et al., 2003). DSSAT is a deterministic modeling platform simulating the daily interactions between soil-plant-atmosphere-crop management as impacted by water and nutritional stresses. The crop model requires inputs (e.g. soil, daily weather, agronomic management) and requires calibration for the crop being considered (e.g. calibration of the wheat or potato varieties used). This cropping system modeling system has been used since the early 1990s, and from 1993 to 2022 it has been cited 10,000 times without self-citations (source Web of Science). It is therefore a robust platform for such studies, having been extensively used for climate change impact testing (Cammarano et al., 2022; Jägermeyr et al., 2021; Rosenzweig et al., 2014). The DSSAT model includes a common mechanism for simulating water and energy balance and nutrient movements between the soil and the plant. In addition, it contains several generic crop models having the ability to simulate 42 crops (e.g. from wheat to pineapple). It can be freely downloaded from www.dssat.net and the source code is freely available on github (<https://github.com/DSSAT/dssat-csm-os>) allowing easy reproduction of results presented.

Appendix B:

SSP1-2.6 is a scenario experiment based on the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways SSP1 with low climate change mitigation and adaptation challenges and the Representative Concentration Pathway RCP2.3, a future pathway with a radiative forcing of 2.6 W m⁻² in the year 2100. SSP5-8.5 is a scenario experiment based on the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways SSP5 in which climate change mitigation challenges dominate and the Representative Concentration Pathway

RCP8.5, a future pathway with a radiative forcing of 8.5 W m⁻² in the year 2100. The SSP1-2.6 depicts a “best case” future from a sustainability perspective, while the SSP5-8.5 scenario represents the high end of plausible future forcing pathways.

Imprint

Publisher:

The James Hutton Institute
Dundee, UK
www.hutton.ac.uk

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Permalink: zenodo.org/record/7247960

The project SOLACE – “Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use” is supported by the European Union’s HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no 727247, and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 17.00094. The opinions expressed and arguments employed herein do not necessarily reflect the official views of the EC and the Swiss government. Neither the European Commission/SERI nor any person acting behalf of the Commission/SERI is responsible for the use which might be made of the information provided on this policy brief.

SOLACE: This policy brief was elaborated in the SOLACE project. The project is running from May 2017 to September 2022. The goal of SOLACE (Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use) is to help European agriculture face major challenges, notably increased rainfall variability and reduced use of N and P fertilizers.

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727247 (SOLACE)

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